

**ON THE FEATURES OF EXPRESSING EXCLAMATIONS IN
THE FRENCH LANGUAGE (BASED ON MONOSYLLABIC
WORDS)**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15316375>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th April 2025

Accepted: 29th April 2025

Online: 30th April 2025

KEYWORDS

Exclamations, imperative sentences, monosyllabic words, semantics, pragmatics, intonation, emotions, communicative functions.

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the features of expressing exclamations and imperative sentences in the French language based on monosyllabic words. The article, considering modern approaches in linguistics, examines the communicative functions of exclamations and imperative sentences, as well as their semantic and pragmatic characteristics. It demonstrates how monosyllabic words, their intonation, and pronunciation are used in the French language to express emotions and give commands. Furthermore, the article analyzes interjections, their meanings, and how they are used in everyday speech, along with their role and significance from a pragmatic perspective.

In the current stage of linguistic development, modern linguistics places particular emphasis on studying the functional aspects of language. Language, first and foremost, serves as a means of communication among people in specific social contexts and with concrete purposes. In this communicative process, imperative and exclamatory sentences play a crucial role in helping the speaker convey certain information or prompt a specific action. These types of sentences are primarily expressed in spoken language, and when analyzed from semantic and pragmatic perspectives, the differences between them become clearly evident.

In imperative sentences, the speaker demands that the listener carry out a specific action. For example, *Va!* ("Go"), *Dis!* ("Say") — in such sentences, the action is clearly requested or commanded. This characteristic defines their communicative function. Moreover, these types of sentences are pronounced with a distinctive intonation and are always directed at the second person.

In French, imperative sentences (*les phrases impératives*) express actions such as commands, advice, suggestions, requests, and prohibitions. They are formed using the imperative mood of verbs and are typically used without an explicit subject. In these cases, the address is conveyed directly through the verb form.

It is worth noting that in expressing this type of sentence, the role, intonation, and pronunciation of monosyllabic words are of particular importance. Monosyllabic words, by definition, consist of only one syllable when pronounced. They are usually short and belong to the group of most frequently used everyday lexical items. Such words are also frequently found in exclamatory and imperative sentences. Especially in spoken language, monosyllabic words play an essential role in expressing emotions, commands, desires, and objections.

Below, we can observe the use of imperative sentences in various communicative functions:

Communicative function:	Imperative sentences	Uzbek interpretation:
Command	<i>Va!</i>	<i>Bor! — Go!</i>
	<i>Viens!</i>	<i>Kel! — Come!</i>
	<i>Cours!</i>	<i>Yugur! — Run!</i>
	<i>Lâche!</i>	<i>Qo'y! Qo'yib yubor! — Stop! / Let go!</i>
	<i>Pars!</i>	<i>Ket! — Leave! / Go away!</i>
	<i>Sors!</i>	<i>Chiq! — Go out!</i>
	<i>Prends!</i>	<i>O! — Take it!</i>
	<i>Tais – toi!</i>	<i>Jim bo'l! — Be quiet!</i>
Request, Advice	<i>Calme – toi!</i>	<i>Tinchlan! — Calm down!</i>
	<i>Parle – moi!</i>	<i>Menga gapir! — Talk to me!</i>
	<i>Dites – moi ce qu'il a dit!</i>	<i>U nima deganini menga ayting! — Tell me what he/she said!</i>
	<i>Aide!</i>	<i>Yordam ber! — Help!</i>
	<i>Viens!</i>	<i>Kel! — Come! (Repeated)</i>
Prohibition	<i>Non!</i>	<i>Yo'q! — No!</i>
	<i>Pas ça!</i>	<i>Bunday qilma! — Don't do that!</i>
	<i>Ne crie pas!</i>	<i>Baqirma! — Don't shout!</i>
	<i>Ne pars pas!</i>	<i>Ketma! — Don't go!</i>
	<i>Ne fais pas ça!</i>	<i>Buni qilma! — Don't do this!</i>

It should be noted that through such sentences, the speaker commands, gives advice, or forbids the listener from performing a certain action. This is likely why imperative sentences are considered one of the influential tools in communication.

Moreover, imperative sentences are primarily expressed using verbs. In French, in addition to verbal imperative sentences, there are also nominal imperative sentences (phrases impératives nominales). For example, *Silence!* (Be quiet!); *Attention!* (Be careful!). However, in the analyzed monosyllabic imperative sentences, nominal imperative sentences were not encountered. Generally, the communicative functions of imperative sentences take place directly within the process of communication, and each action performed within this process is aimed at achieving a specific goal.

In exclamatory sentences, the speaker expresses their emotions or inner feelings such as joy, happiness, surprise, sorrow, or regret. For example, *Zut!* (Wow!) – an expression of surprise or regret in response to an unexpected situation; *Tiens!* (Look!) – an expression of surprise or amazement, drawing attention. These sentences are also pronounced with a special intonation.

In French, exclamatory sentences (*les phrases exclamatives*) are used to express strong emotions and feelings such as surprise, joy, anger, and fear, often through intense intonation. These sentences usually begin with *que*, *comme*, or the determiner *quel* (or its variations: *quelle*, *quels*, *quelles*) and end with an exclamation mark. For example, *Quel beau temps!* (What

beautiful weather!) – this sentence expresses surprise or joy about a beautiful day; or *Comme c'est triste!* (How sad!) – this expresses sadness or despair.

In our study, among the everyday lexical items analyzed, a small number of monosyllabic exclamatory sentences were identified. Some examples include:

- *Bonne chance!* – a positive wish; encouragement.
- *Quelle chance!* – surprise, positive astonishment.
- *Pas du tout!* – rejection, disagreement.

In the French language, alongside exclamatory sentences, interjections are also considered linguistic units that express emotions indirectly through short, emotionally charged lexical elements. Interjections are a part of speech used to express emotional reactions to the surrounding environment or to urge a certain action. These words are grammatically invariable — they do not change form, are independent, and are often composed of a single syllable. Typically, they form a separate sentence and are not grammatically connected to other words.

In French, such words are used to express a variety of emotions such as joy, surprise, anger, or pain. Furthermore, interjections usually appear at the beginning of a sentence and reflect the speaker's emotional attitude in relation to the content of the utterance. For example, if we pay attention to the analysis of commonly used monosyllabic interjections in everyday French, we can observe this expressive function in action:

Interjections	Pronunciation	Semantic Feature / Meaning	Usage / Context of use
Ah!	[a]	<i>Astonishment, drawing attention, discontent, irony</i>	<i>Ah, ça alors!</i>
Oh!	[o]	<i>Indifference, disdain</i>	<i>Oh! Tu m'as fait peur!</i>
Eh!	[ɛ]	<i>Indifference, disregard</i>	<i>Eh! toi là-bas!</i> <i>Eh! t'as vu ça!</i>
Bah!	[ba]	<i>Regret, unexpected situation, anger</i>	<i>Bah, ça m'est égal!</i>
Pff!	[pf]	<i>Silence, warning</i>	<i>Pff, j'en ai marre!</i>
Zut!	[zyt]	<i>Astonishment, drawing attention, discontent, irony</i>	<i>Zut! Trop tard!</i>
Chut!	[ʃyt]	<i>Indifference, disdain</i>	<i>Chut! Il dort.</i>

In everyday French, frequently used monosyllabic interjections stand out for their brevity and expressive power in spoken language. Our analysis reveals that some of these interjections are actually onomatopoeic, meaning they simultaneously mimic sounds and convey emotions.

Overall, the use of interjections is directly linked to the context of communication, where their pragmatic functions become especially evident. As scholar Sh. Safarov notes: *"Just as the world is full of colorful and diverse events and phenomena, so too are the situations in which communication occurs. These situations arise in various conditions and environments."*

Indeed, in different communicative settings, the functional-semantic and pragmatic characteristics of interjections become strikingly clear. For instance, if we examine the pragmatic function of the interjection **"Ah!"** in each of the sentences below, we can observe how its meaning shifts depending on the context.

1. – *Ah! C'est vous, monsieur, répondit le Français. – Ah! It's you, sir," said the Frenchman.* The interjection "Ah!" here expresses delighted surprise or sudden recognition, conveying an immediate emotional reaction.

2. – *Ah! Mon maître! Mon maître! – Ah! My teacher! My teacher!* This expression likely conveys a strong emotional feeling, possibly indicating pain, despair, or fear.

3. – *Ah ça! que voulez – vous dire! demanda Fix. – Ah, what are you trying to say! – said Fix.* The interjection "Ah!" expresses anger, confusion, or disagreement in relation to the previous statements, intensifying the following question and making it more impactful and clearer.

The interjection "Ah!" in each of the given sentences does not convey factual information, but rather directly expresses an emotional, immediate reaction. This situation clearly demonstrates the pragmatic function of the interjection, which is not an exaggeration. In the process of speech, the use of interjections indicates the strength of the interactive dynamics.

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